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Competencies and Values of Barangay Nutrition Scholars in Eastern Visayas: Basis for Program Development

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Abstract

The study determined the competencies and values of Barangay Nutrition Scholars (BNS) in Eastern Visayas and the relationship between the said variables along the sociodemographic variables, which formed as bases in proposing for a capacity training development program for BNS in the local community. The study utilized the quantitative research design in determining the values and competencies of the BNS. The respondents of the study were the selected BNSs working with the MNAO from the provinces of Samar, Leyte and Southern Leyte. Descriptive and inferential statistics were employed to measure and analyze the variables. The sociodemographic data revealed an unequal representation of BNS in terms of the different sociodemographic categories. In terms of the level of competence, most BNSs perceived themselves as “moderately competent” in planning and in mobilizing resource, while BNSs perceived themselves as “competent” in coordinating, documenting and record keeping, implementing, and monitoring and evaluating. It is important to note that there was a significant positive relationship between age, educational attainment, length of service, and the number trainings attended of the BNSs with their level of competence and practice of core values in the workplace. It is imperative to formulate a simplified version and an extensive practical approach to nutrition education training needs to be looked into when designing and modifying the existing programs.

Keywords: *nutrition scholars, correlational study, work competence, nutrition education training*

Introduction

Community Health Workers (CHWs) such as Barangay Nutrition Scholars (BNSs) are considered important stakeholders in the advancement of community health but their roles in public health are often unrecognized. These key individuals comprise the frontier of basic healthcare in several localities because several communities rely on them on the access of various health services. Nonetheless, the mechanisms to which CHWs are employed efficiently remains to be vague and there is scarce data about their specific training demands and needs. As such, extensive research on the competencies, values, and knowledge among BNSs or CHWs is needed.

Barangay Nutrition Scholars (BNSs) play an important role in the successful implementation of the Philippine Plan of Action for Nutrition (PPAN) 2017-2022, an integral part of the Philippine Development Plan (PDP), on which it is a Medium-Term Plan of development to address poverty. These workers are those that focus on the promotion of good health through good nutrition and primary prevention of nutrition related illness in the population (PHN, 2017). Appropriate skills especially training for health workers presents a potential entry point in improving the nutrition situation among children and the community (Sunguya et al, 2013).

Although BNS and Barangay Health Worker (BHW) are both Community Health Workers, the BHW is a person who has undergone training programs under any accredited government and non-government organization and who voluntarily renders primary health care services in the community after having been accredited to function as such by the local health board in accordance with the guidelines promulgated by the DOH as prescribed by Republic Act 7883.

The Barangay Nutrition Scholars was created in 1978 by virtue of Presidential Decree No. 1569 in order to provide an effective means of disseminating nutrition information and providing nutrition services to the barangays through a trained community worker. The BNS project was pilot tested in 1977 in 13 municipalities and by the end of 1979, 5,220 BNSs had been trained and deployed in their communities. At least one BNS is needed every barangay where he or she is a resident and is able to speak the local dialect and at least 18 years old but not more than 60 years old. The BNS shall be recruited from within the barangay and shall be tested on mental ability and proper work ability. BNS are considered the front liners in providing the basic health and nutrition services to their communities. Also, the Food and Nutrition Research Institute (FNRI), deemed them as the “key implementers” of the numerous grassroots projects of the government as they are in direct contact with the barangay and its members. The new recruited BNS shall attend the training on Basic Course for BNS to provide them common basic knowledge and skills. Introduced in the training are the roles and functions such as planning, coordination, advocacy and promotion, implementation, monitoring and evaluation, resource mobilization and documentation and record keeping. Likewise, the BNS should possess the values as introduced in the training such as integrity, transparency, efficiency, equity, excellence in work, respect for human rights and accountability (Gavilan, 2014).

UNICEF (2017) in a study about the cost of undernutrition indicated that the country loses Php220 billion annually or about 1.5% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) because of malnutrition. The Barangay Nutrition Scholar Program supervised by the National Nutrition Council (NNC) shall allocate one (1) barangay nutrition scholar in every barangay. The barangay-based volunteer, BNS, cover numerous works in the delivery of nutrition and other related activities for the improvement of nutrition situation in the barangay. The blueprint of the BNS in the implementation of activities is the PPAN 2017-2022 which lay down the framework to improve the quality of the human resource in the country. The general outcome of the framework is to reduce stunting, wasting, obesity, and

micronutrient deficiencies. The BNS as the focal for nutrition program at the barangay level shall implement activities such as nutrition advocacy, backyard gardening and food production, environmental health and sanitation, psychosocial interventions, family planning and other nutrition related activities.

The NNC Governing Board (GB) Resolution No. 2, series of 2012, specifies the conduct of the Operation Timbang Plus (OPT+) to children 0-59 months during the first quarter of the year. The survey is conducted by the BNSs nationwide. One of the necessary skills for a BNS is the ability to document, do reporting and recording of documents and present reports. Parallel to documentation, the BNS shall also facilitate and assist the Barangay Nutrition Committee (BNC) in the conduct of planning workshop to come up a sound doable barangay nutrition action plan (BNS Basic Course, 2013). GB Resolution No. 2 is stating that health worker to include the BNS shall be responsible in producing quality data to make a better analysis on nutrition situation.

PD 1569, Section 7 states that the BNS shall undergo a ten-day competency training on important topics such as nutrition aspects, health conditions, food production procedure, and environmental sanitation, which are basic core areas on defined task expectations. The role of the BNS in the achievement of malnutrition is highly demanded. The Department of Health as prime mover in the delivery of services, implements the nutrition specific programs. These programs address the immediate causes of malnutrition. Hence, the presence of BNS is needed in the identification of children for management of severely acute malnourished children in the Philippine Integrated Management of Acute Malnutrition Program (PIMAP). BNSs likewise assist in the National Dietary Supplementation Program (NDSP), Micronutrient Supplementation Program (MSP) such as giving of Vitamin A, iron-folic supplementation for pregnant women, and community advocacy of food fortification. The task of the BNS as stipulated in the law is very crucial granting that a human resource based is to develop. The result of barangay nutrition worker's action could directly contribute in shaping the overall health, and socioeconomic landscape of the country as this manifestation is carried through adulthood (Save the Children, 2016). Being a BNS is a challenging job because the future of the children is in their hands (Gavilan, 2014).

In the Philippines, there is a quantifiable number of well-trained and qualified professionals working to deliver social services especially for children's health and nutrition (UNICEF, 2018). In Eastern Visayas, according to NNC Regional Office, there are 4,849 BNSs in 2019. However, the number of trained BNSs varies as in the new Barangay Chairperson take hold of the position every after election, another set of barangay health workers are identified including the selection of the BNS. At the barangay level, the BNC provides administrative supervision to the BNS. Administratively, the BNS are under the LGU and is supervised by the City/Municipal Nutrition Action Officer at the municipal or city level and technically supervised by the District/City Nutrition Program Coordinator. The different municipalities within the province directly communicate with the Provincial Nutrition Action Officer (PNAO). The notable shortage of trained manpower provides limited supply of basic services which hinders full development to fulfil children's rights.

Thus, this study was proposed because of several rationalizations. Foremost is the need to provide empirical monitoring of the current status of BNS in Eastern Visayas since they are an important aspect in the delivery of basic health services to the general public. The study is also rationalized by the legal mandates of the state, as reflected in the aforesaid national decrees, to uphold the health and socioeconomic conditions of the Filipino people through the implementation of an efficient nutrition program. Furthermore, the need to investigate the implementation of a national program in the local setting, as noted in the aforementioned discussion, is imperative. Albeit there have been local studies that investigated BNS competencies, it is noted that there is a dearth of documented studies in Eastern Visayas that focused on the competencies and values of BNS and the relationship of these variables with each other and with certain demographic factors. At the experiential level, the researcher, being a government employee with direct interaction with the BNS, has documented several instances wherein the BNS has poor competencies in the delivery of basic service in the local community. It is for these propositions that this research was proposed and its ultimate goal is to formulate a capacity training development program in order to ameliorate the effectiveness of BNS program in Eastern Visayas where he is assigned.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the competencies and values of Barangay Nutrition Scholar (BNS). Specifically, the study answered the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the Barangay Nutrition Scholar in terms of
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. gender;
 - 1.3. civil status;
 - 1.4. educational attainment;
 - 1.5. length of service as bns;
 - 1.6. number of trainings/seminars attended related to bns;
 - 1.7. and number of awards received as bns?
2. What is the competency level of Barangay Nutrition Scholars as rated by the Nutrition Action Officer and the Barangay Nutrition Scholars themselves in terms of the following:
 - 2.1. planning;
 - 2.2. coordinating;
 - 2.3. implementation;

- 2.4. monitoring and evaluation;
- 2.5. resource mobilization; and
- 2.6. documentation and record keeping?
3. Is there a difference in the Barangay Nutrition Scholars level of competencies across raters?
4. What is the extent by which the following values are practiced by the Barangay Nutrition Scholar as assessed by the Nutrition Action Officer and the Barangay Nutrition Scholars themselves, along the following:
 - 4.1. integrity;
 - 4.2. transparency;
 - 4.3. efficiency;
 - 4.4. equity;
 - 4.5. excellence in work;
 - 4.6. respect for human rights; and
 - 4.7. accountability?
5. Is there a relationship between the level of the Barangay Nutrition Scholars competencies and their:
 - 5.1. profile variables;
 - 5.2. values employed in the workplace?
6. Which of the identified variables best predict the competencies of the Barangay Nutrition Scholars?
7. What development program maybe proposed based on the findings of the study?

Literature Review

Needed Improvement on Public Health Nutrition

Capacity in its simplest definition pertains to the potential to perform objectives (Goodman, 1998) that could be work related. Relating to the practice of Public Health Nutrition, it refers to the sustainable capability at a number stages that involves personal, organizational, and workforce among others that are needed to perform successfully and efficiently in attaining goals like enhancement of health (Horton et al, 2003).

Capacity building on the other hand was described substantially with the aid of health scholars and experts. One definition immediately offers with the upkeep and development of a number of capital factors such as human, social, physical and natural as key gamers for the improvement of the staff and the exercise of the profession. The association of these terminologies to each other had led for the creation of their very own meanings and eventually making them phase of health advertising (Hawe et al, 1998; Horton, 2002; Crisp, Swerissen and Duckett, 2000; and Joffres et al, 2004). The NSW Health (2001) and Strategic Inter Governmental Nutrition Alliance (2001) defined capacity-building as a non-stop method focusing on improving health and health-related sectors in order to have more than one health gains, via to the improvement of sustainable skills, structures, resources and commitment. In addition, it seeks to answer certain health troubles delivered through inequality and exclusion in the society by means of increasing abilities of people, groups and communities in addressing and preserving health and offering health services.

Other health professionals defined potential improvement synonymously anchoring on the sustainable improvement of individuals, groups and societies by growing their potentials to achieve objectives, clear up problems, and apprehend their development desires (Horton et al, 2003). Furthermore, Labonte et al. (2002) pertains to capacity constructing as a strategy to development but believed that certain factors must be current in order to gain health targets and fortify communities, may it be grassroots, inter-organizational partnerships, or networks of agencies. On a different note, Rifkin (2003) perceives it greater of a non-public manner whereby persons acquire knowledge, skills, and confidence in developing their own selves.

Wescott (2002) perceived potential improvement as an enhancement of the capabilities and capacities of the human beings and institutions, highlighting that this can be executed by giving interest to body of workers and assets management discovered through health education and coaching. La Fond, Brown and Macintyre (2002) recommended ways on how to strengthen the potential of health institutions and its workers, highlighting the necessity to improve in statistics go with the flow and via obtaining quite a number health resources.

Another important variable of the study is anchored on the skills, competencies, and proficiencies of BNS. Visker, Rhodes, and Cox (2017) outlined the common tasks carried out by CHWs. Key informants recognized supplying health education, connecting human beings with scientific offerings or programs, and connecting human beings with non-medical offerings or applications as major tasks. They argued that CHWs' pinnacle solutions blanketed connecting people with medical offerings or programs, connecting people with non-medical offerings or programs, and supplying health education.

Additionally, Rosenthal, Rush, and Allen (2016) recognized the need for a robust evaluation on the roles and competencies of CHWs, the formulation of a basic expertise source, and methods to verify ability aptitude amongst CHWs. Snyder (2016) states that "given their strong bonds with communities and capability to facilitate access, coordination, potential building, and service delivery, CHWs are seen as one conceivable solution..." (p. 4). Landers and Levinson (2016) additionally forecast the future need of CHWs to assist in the mitigation of a harassed health care machine and to probably reduce health care costs.

The Pan-Canadian Task Force on Public Health Nutrition Practice (2009) proposed a framework in achieving a strong and environment friendly public nutrition. The framework counseled those abilities are requirements in performing public health jobs and fundamental cores for public health competencies. These skills are in the form of skills, understanding and attitudes that directly answer public health wants of the population: outline the public health personnel for the purposes of creating a plan, collect important data on the state health workforce, become aware of the basic public health services, identify core public health competencies, discover feature precise health proficiency, advance employee competency assessment equipment and incentives, align education programs to reflect expertise and inter-professional practice, map the abilities of every discipline in opposition to the core and function-specific competencies, improve organizational assessment tools and incentives, development recruitment/retention strategies to entice required competencies, strengthen constructions to guide inter-professional training (space, time, instructors), deploy personnel in inter-professional fashions based totally on their competencies, discover excellent practices in inter-professional deployment, pick out first-class practices in recruitment and retention, discover best practices in schooling (including placements, continuing education) and advance accreditation standards/ first-rate manipulate measures.

One of the research projects that explores the nutrition-related competencies needed in healthcare is that of Etherton et al (2015). What makes this study relevant to the current research is that it highlights the abilities in controlling clinical instruction and the critical need to build up capabilities in nourishment related patient consideration, which are competencies among BNS. It also shares similar research objectives with the present study because it advocates a competency-based nourishment training approach for medical services experts to address issues of clinical and general well-being sustenance for the counteraction and therapy of numerous intense, transferable, and ceaseless infections. Nonetheless, the said research targets a wide range health care and medical professionals and not solely focused on BNS.

In the research of Gopalan et al (2012), the motivation and performance of the different community health workers (CHWs) and the various correlates of these motivation levels on a health program are explored. It was discovered that the motivation level in the research participants' performance was at the strongest in terms of individual and community factors. It was the health system variables that obtained the least scores. What is important to note in the said study is that the community and system-level recognition were found to be significantly correlated to the participants' higher levels of earnings community health workers. This also includes their sense of social responsibility and the value of self-efficacy in terms of their accountability. Mainstreaming of gender in the health approach of the community particularly on the participation and involvement of stakeholders were the positive roles of the CHW program. The use of the gender variable is an important research objective of the said study which makes it a relevant empirical work.

Similar to the current research, Aseyo et al (2018) affirm various variables that can impact the competency and effectiveness of community health workers (CHWs) in the delivery of basic services related to health of the local community, both at the individual and at the wider program-based level. Different sets of contextual variables, such as norms of culture and society, economic challenges to require in health services and care facilities, challenges of access related to location and geography, policies related to the health system, and functionality aspects, have all been affirmed to affect the performance and efficiency of CHWs. It affirmed that conditions associated to comfortable working environment, justifiable working hours, and making it certain that health workers are not overworked with duties could ameliorate their overall performance and efficiency. These are all imperative to have sufficient conditions for a comprehensive role in the delivery of target healthcare services in the community.

In another research, Ngugi et al (2018) measure community health workers and volunteers' level of attrition and the different predictors of their performance in a rural region of Kenya. It was affirmed that weak interest and motivation in peer organization involvement was statistically related with attrition. The absence or lack of continuous training and education coupled with the experience of having no feedback from the health care workers' supervisors were also significantly related with attrition levels. It is also affirmed that discordance in the health care volunteers' expectations and their perception in having a heavy workload during the process of carrying out their duties were identified and significantly affirmed as key predictors for attrition in the said study. This justifies the inclusion of the trainings attended and the values of BNS as one of the variables in the present research so that its generalizability as an independent variable could be tested in the local setting.

One related work on the capacity development program for community health volunteers (CHV) is that of Vareilles et al (2017). They specifically identified broad capacity intervention approaches such as considering the CHV to be entities inside the community, affirmation of clear or defined roles, conducting different skill-based and continuous training opportunities, incentives and rewards system institutionalization, improving the process of supervision and logistical assistance to promote effectiveness in task distribution and promulgation. The practices identified in the said research are pragmatic data that can be used by program developers, policymakers in various levels of the organization, donors of public health programs, and the community itself. Because one of the research objectives is to formulate a capacity development program for BNS, the aforementioned insights are practical to consider.

Role of the Barangay Nutrition Scholars

Most of the local literatures focus on the role and importance of BNS. For example, Baguilat (2016) argued that primary health workers like BNS and BHWs have the foremost direct impact on the health and nutrition of community members, notably pregnant mothers and youngsters 0-2 years previous. The primary purpose of contact within the health system is through numerous means of consultations at the medical institution, home visits and grassroots health promotion activities.

According to Aglipay-Villar (2016), author of House Bill No. 766, “Barangay Nutrition Students play a crucial role during this fight, serving on the front-lines in their communities, guaranteeing that national and native government nutrition policies area unit enforced at the grassroots level.” BNS should have bound leadership credentials, and area unit chosen by the chief of the barangay council or the barangay nutrition committee. This is further supported by the minimum qualifications as mandated by the Presidential Decree No. 1659 which shall be as follows: (1) Bonafide residence on the barangay for a minimum of four years, with ability to talk the dialect; (2) Possession of leadership potentials and therefore the initiative and disposition to serve the barangay for a minimum of one year; (3) Disposition to find out, and to show what he has learned to the barangay people; (4) At minimum an elementary school graduate; (5) Physical and mental fitness; and (6) at a minimum eighteen (18) years of age yet not more than sixty (60) years of age. The barangay sustenance researcher will be enlisted from inside the barangay and will be tried on mental capacity and appropriate work state of mind.

Matos et al (2011) in their report, depicted the extent of training among CHW as, "...should be viewed as a comprehensive rundown of jobs and errands which CHWs...may be relied upon to satisfy," where they are utilized to satisfy at least one relegated assignment, yet these duties shift from association to association. Moreover, this work structure gives wide-cluster of duties to profession improvement, wherein specialization or speculation among CHWs are conceivable relying upon the quantity of jobs they can perform or of expert on.

The nourishment program depends on four (4) intercession plans: food production, food assistance, health protection, and information, education and communication (IEC). The BNS is the sustenance program's instrument for actualizing these mediation plans. As per Segment 7 of Presidential Announcement No. 1659, "preceding genuine barangay benefit, the Barangay Nourishment Researcher will experience a ten-day preparing on chosen subjects, for example, sustenance, wellbeing, nourishment creation, and ecological sanitation, in light of characterized assignment desires, to be directed by a commonplace preparing group as a team with the city and the barangay nourishment panels. This preparation will be enhanced by a twenty-day practicum to be directed in the barangay, where the researcher is allotted, and such action will be as a team with a nearby preparing group. There is no far-reaching study known to the scientist that surveys the abilities and estimations of BNS in the Philippines.

Additionally, CHW sub-jobs were characterized by C3 Project (2016) as takes after the following: (1) Social Intervention Among People, People Group, and Wellbeing and Social Administration Frameworks; (2) Giving Socially Proper Wellbeing Instruction and Data; (3) Care Coordination, Case Administration, and Framework Route; (4) Giving Instructing and Social Help; (5) Pushing for People and Networks; (6) Building Individual and Network Limit; (7) Giving Direct Administration; (8) Executing Individual and Network Appraisals; (9) Directing Effort; and (10) Partaking in Assessment and Exploration.

Previous local literature focusing on the competency enhancement of neighborhood health nutrition personnel was once limited. Africa (2014) reported BNS in two provinces in CALABARZON to have the information on breastfeeding, complementary feeding, counseling, and IYCF-related items; mindset such as self-belief of BNS on IYCF Counseling, understanding on accountability, perceived problems on IYCF Counseling, and grasp on IYCF Counseling Implementation; and capabilities on constructing rapport and giving assisted skills, learning and listening skills, assessment and analysis, and action skills. Knowledge, mindset and capabilities of educated BNS on IYCF counseling in two CALABARZON provinces need improvement. However, Africa did not provide concrete tips as to how BNS will enhance its KAS on IYCF Counseling by setting up a set of competency abilities and values.

Moreover, the House Bill No. 776 of Representative Aglipay-Villar proposes persevering with training for BNS “to improve competencies throughout the formal training, the BNS shall attend month-to-month meetings at some point of which the District/City Nutrition Program Coordinator (D/CNPC) or Nutrition Action Officer (NAO) shall furnish extra facts to update their understanding and skills. The D/CNPC or NAO shall conduct everyday visits to study and inspire the BINS to function their duties successfully and effectively.” The lawmaker also recommends improving benefits, privileges, and incentives of BNS commensurate to the necessary position that they play in the community.

In this light, Baguilat (2016) explained that House Bill No. 3564 is useful in resolving the trouble of malnutrition entails that these health employees are poorly compensated, sufficiently capacitated, and efficaciously protected. Although each BHW and BNS are labeled as volunteers, the measly and discretionary amount they acquire as allowances and honoraria do no longer supply them the dignity and awareness they deserve for their critical work. They also did no longer acquire non-stop getting to know opportunities to beautify the best of their offerings apart from the preliminary training prior to deployment.

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized the descriptive-correlational research design to determine the level of competence and practice of core values in the workplace among Barangay Nutrition Scholars, as well as the relationship between selected profile variables and these variables. According to Sousa et al (2007), descriptive-correlational design is applicable when the focus of the study is to “describe the variables and the relationships that occur naturally between and among them.” Thus, this design was deemed appropriate to address the objectives of this study.

Moreover, the survey method was used in collecting data. Data analysis was carried out by using both descriptive and inferential

statistics, including frequencies, percentages, means, Pearson's r , point-biserial correlation, Spearman's ρ , eta correlation, and standard multiple regression analysis.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were 155 selected BNSs working with the MNAO in the three (3) provinces of the region, namely: Samar, Leyte and Southern Leyte or the research locale. The identified respondents were also then rated by their respective supervisors, the MNAOs. There are 4,449 BNSs in the region in 2017 where 642 in Samar, 1,756 BNSs in Leyte and 508 BNSs in Southern Leyte. The BNS are distributed and appointed by their respective LGUs by means and ways: a typical assignment was one BNS for each designated per barangay as stated in PD 1569. Thus, a one-is-to-one ratio was ideal in any given LGU-setup. The G-Power software was used to conduct a priori power analysis to estimate the sufficient sample size for the study. With an anticipated effect size of 0.15 for 8 independent/predictor variables, the estimated minimum sample size to achieve a statistical power level of 0.80 was 116. To provide a better picture of the study, the sample size was increased to 155.

Another round of the same sampling methodology was employed per province of choice to fully operate the study randomly sampling the necessary representation. To calculate the number of samples, the specialized G power analysis specified to input hypothesis test was and the different predictor variables. In the determination of the significant predictors of level of competence and practice of core values, the multiple regression analyses were performed. The predictor variables were: age, sex, civil status, education, length of service, number of trainings and number of awards. The total breakdown of the population and sample size of the research respondents of 155 were distributed as 39 samples in Samar, 80 samples for Leyte and 36 samples in Southern Leyte.

Instrument

The research instruments consisted of three parts. Part I focuses on the profile of the respondents which include the respondents' code, age, sex, civil status, other job, educational attainment, length of service as BNS and trainings seminars attended. This part was researcher-made section and there was no validation needed since this was basic demographic information related to the BNS. Retrieval of this instrument from the respondents was done together with the other sections of the questionnaire.

Part II covered questions on the BNS competencies. This part was divided into items for planning, coordination, implementation, monitoring and evaluation, resource generation/ mobilization and documentation and record keeping. A total of 51 items were rated for the BNS competence. Administration and retrieval of this instrument was done in a single day in order to avoid loss of data. This was facilitated with the assistance of the local government units.

Part III measured the practice of the BNS as to integrity, transparency, efficiency, equity, excellence in work, respect for human rights and accountability. A total of 35 items are measured under the Part II questionnaire on values. Furthermore, these values were part of the formation of the BNS through the INTEERAct, which is the values restoration and good moral and right conduct formation program of the National Nutrition Council and Civil Service Commission (CSC). Since this is part of the major research instrument, retrieval process for this section was done applying the same strategies.

Procedure

The researcher followed the protocol and procedures set by the Graduate School in undergoing this research. Foremost, a letter to the university addressed to the Graduate School Dean was sent with the proposed research title and proposal as attached. The approval of the research title sought for the selection of the research adviser and expanding the research proposal to a full format research design with supporting evidences. This is once discussed in plenary during the pre-oral defense with a panel of experts on which upon approval, the data gathering commences.

It is a standard protocol to send a letter to the head offices of the concerned research local, particularly the local chief executives and seek for their approval to conduct the said research study. After the requests granted, the researcher immediately started the identification of the research participants to the preselected municipalities and barangays that this research was covering.

After seeking for the administrative approval and clearances, the researcher had a courtesy call to the LCE or their Administrative Officer or to the Municipal Health Officer. The researcher was the one who administered the survey questionnaire of the respondents. A separate consent for the respondents was prepared and was given to ensure the anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents. Before the BNS answered the survey questionnaire, the researcher explained the objectives of the research as for the respondents to have a clearer view of what the study aims to achieve.

The same concept was done to the MNAO as the supervisor respondent who evaluated the BNS with the same statement of questions. This process was done routinely by the researcher throughout the various research locale and respondents that he visited during the data-gathering.

On the course of the data gathering, the researcher handed over the letter for the research participants and a demographic data sheet for each of the respondent to fill in. For the unfinished survey forms, the MNAO is requested to supervise the administration of the form and requested to send via courier, scanned copies and send via email or forward through public utility van. After administering the survey, the researcher started with the tabulation of data results.

Data Analysis

For the data analyses of this study, the following descriptive and inferential statistics were employed:

Eta Correlation Coefficient (η). This measures the strength of relationship between a categorical variable and a continuous variable, with the former treated as the independent measure and the latter the dependent measure. For this study, in particular, respondents' civil status was the independent measure while their competence and practice of core values were the dependent measures.

Frequencies and Percentages. These were used to summarize and describe the distribution of the number of respondents across the levels of the profile variables.

Mean. Mean of both self-assessment scores and observer scores were used to determine the respondents' level of competence and practice of core values in the workplace.

Pearson r. This was used in this study to measure the strength of relationship between profile variables measured at the ratio level and respondents' competence and practice of core values. The profile variables at the ratio scale in this study included age, length of service, number of trainings attended, and number awards received.

Point-Biserial Correlation Coefficient (rpb). This measures the strength of relationship between a dichotomous categorical variable and a continuous variable. Specifically, this was used to assess the relationship between respondents' sex and their competence and practice of core values. For purposes of interpretation, the following codes were used: 0 for females, 1 for males.

Spearman's Rho (r_s). This was used to measure the strength of relationship between respondents' competence and practice of core values, and the variables educational attainment and prevalence of malnutrition, both measured at the ordinal level. For purposes of interpretation, variable levels were coded. For educational attainment, the codes were: 1 = elementary level, 2 = elementary graduate, 3 = high school level, 4 = high school graduate, 5 = college level, 6 = college graduate. For prevalence of malnutrition, the codes were: 1 = low, 2 = medium, 3 = high.

Standard Multiple Regression Analysis. Standard Multiple Regression Analyses were performed to determine the significant predictors of level of competence and practice of core values among the respondents. This statistical technique provides standardized coefficients known as Beta coefficients or Beta-weights which allow the comparison of the relative or individual effects of the predictor variables on the criterion variables.

Meanwhile, because the inclusion of predictor variables with three or more levels into the regression model frequently makes the interpretation of the result exigent, levels of educational attainment in particular were recoded to reduce complexity of result and to possibly reveal more meaningful interpretation (codes: 0 = at most high school level, 1 = at least high school graduate).

However, the codes for the categories of civil status were retained because civil status is a nominal scale, making it difficult to create a borderline between any two categories unlike educational attainment whose categories can be rank ordered, yielding several choices for cut-off points. Meanwhile, three dummy variables were created for civil status since it has four categories – single, married, widow/widower, and separated, with the category “single” taken as the reference group. The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

There is no a significant difference in the Barangay Nutrition Scholars level of competencies across raters.

There is no a significant relationship between the competencies acquired by the Barangay Nutrition Scholars and their.

Profile variables

Values employed in the workplace

None of the identified variables best predict(s) the competencies of the Barangay Nutrition Scholars

Ethical Considerations

All data collected were put with protection and security especially personal information of the research participants as observed in the guidelines and Implementing Rules and Regulations (IRR) set by the Data Privacy Act of 2010 or RA 10173. Each of the BNS and MNAO as a respondent was provided with the consent. The statement of the consent provided the title of the study, the principal investigator and its adviser, background and purpose of the study, and consent statement itself. Likewise, the administration of the survey is voluntary. The respondent BNS was asked to sign his/her signature with the date of signing. The MNAO as the ratee of the BNS was likewise provided with the consent.

Results and Discussion

This section presents and discusses the findings to address the objectives of the study. The discussion highlights the profile of the Barangay Nutrition Scholars (BNSs) – the respondents of the study, and their level of competence and level of practice of certain core values in the workplace based on how they and their respective Municipal Nutrition Action Officers (MNAOs) perceived it. It also

highlights whether there exist substantial relationships or associations between the profile variables and their level of competence and practice of core values, as well as the important predictors of competence and values. Ultimately, a capacity development program for the BNS is put forward.

Profile of the Respondents

The discussions below will give the respondents demographic characteristics and will provide descriptions to their responses.

Age. The respondents of this study as shown in Table 02 were 155 Barangay Nutrition Scholars (BNSs), comprised of 153 females (98.7%) and 2 males (1.3%). The ages of the BNSs by the time they were surveyed range from 21 to 74, with a mean of 44 years and a standard deviation of around 10 years. By age cohort, 9 had ages 29 years and below (5.8%), 50 had ages 30 to 39 years (32.3%), 51 had an age range of 40 to 49 years (32.9%), 31 were of ages 50 to 59 years (20%), and 14 were of ages 60 years and above (9.0%).

It is important to note that the majority of the population of the Barangay Nutrition Scholars are between 40-50 years old. This implies that any training program geared towards the development of their skills as nutrition workers of the community must be in line with this age group. That is to say that capability and enhancement program need to be designed in a manner that considers late adult learners in the area of nutrition education and practice. The said data also implies that the Local Government Units (LGUs) need to encourage young adults to participate in this program.

Sex. Of the 155 respondents, 153 (98.7%) of them are female and only 2 (1.3%) are males. Another important consideration is the pervasiveness of the female gender in the BNS program of the government. This trend of feministic dominance in this occupation need to be considered in program delivery especially in the development of trainings and seminars. Male residents of the barangays need to be encouraged to participate as BNS as well in order to distribute the work opportunities to the different section of the community.

Civil Status. Concerning civil status, 23 reported being single (14.8%), 106 reported being married (68.4%), 9 indicated being widows or widowers (5.8%), and 17 were separated from their spouses (11%). A further inquiry into the motivations of the female to seek more participation in the program than the male residents need to be verified in order to provide more empirical data on the overall program implementation of BNS in the country. Since the majority of BNS in the locale are married, careful monitoring of their commitment and involvement in the program should be implemented. Single residents in the community may be invited for program orientation in order to encourage more participation on their side.

Table 1. *Distribution of the Respondents across Levels of the Profile Variables*

Variable	Categories	Frequency	Percentages
Age	60 years and above	14	9.0
	50 to 59 years old	31	20.0
	40 to 49 years old	51	32.9
	30 to 39 years old	50	32.3
	29 years and below	9	5.8
Sex	Male	2	1.3
	Female	153	98.7
Civil Status	Single	23	14.8
	Married	106	68.4
	Widow/Widower	9	5.8
	Separated	17	11.0
Educational Attainment	College Graduate	12	7.7
	College Level	33	21.3
	High School Graduate	75	48.4
	High School Level	27	17.4
	Elementary Graduate	7	4.5
Length of Service	Elementary Level	1	0.7
	10 years and above	41	26.5
	7 to 9 years	28	18.1
	4 to 6 years	23	14.8
	1 to 3 years	39	25.2
Number of Trainings/ Seminars Attended	less than 1 year	24	15.5
	7 to 9	10	6.5
	4 to 6	39	25.2
	1 to 3	75	48.4
	0	31	20.0
Number of Awards Received	2	1	0.7
	1	14	9.0
	0	140	90.3
Prevalence of Malnutrition	High	39	25.2
	Medium	80	51.6
	Low	36	23.2

Educational Attainment. In terms of educational attainment, 1 had not completed elementary level (0.7%), 7 were elementary graduates (4.5%), 27 had not completed high school level (17.4%), 75 were high school graduates (48.4%), 33 had not finished college (21.3%), and 12 had graduated from college (7.7%).

The large population of BNS who are not college level, comprised approximately 70% of the total number of samples, is important to consider. This means that training and education programs should cater to this group of participants. A simplified version and an extensive practical approach to nutrition education training needs to be looked into when designing and modifying the existing programs for them. This also suggests that the health authorities may revisit the selection criteria for BNS whether those who have attained an educational status below the high school level could be allowed to enter the said program.

Length of Service. As regards length of service of BNSs, 24 (15.5%) respondents have less than a year of experience (15.5%), 39 with 1 to 3 years of experience (25.2%), and 23 with 4 to 6 years of experience (14.8%); meanwhile, 28 had already served for 7 to 9 years (18.1%), and 41 had already served for at least 10 years (26.5%).

It is evident from the demographic results that most of the BNS participants have at least 10 years of experience. This means that their satisfaction in the current program may be high or the program itself provides a good compensation package to them. Such factors may be revisited in future inquiry in order to establish the verity of program effectiveness.

Number of Trainings and Seminars Attended. As to the number of trainings and seminars attended by the respondents, 124 reported that they were trained (80%) while 31 indicated that they had not attended any training or seminar (20%). Moreover, 106 respondents had attended a maximum of only 3 trainings (68.4%), while the remaining 49 had attended a minimum of 4 to a maximum of 9 trainings (31.6%).

A large percentage of the BNS have only 1-3 seminars or trainings attended. Considering their length of years in the program (10 years for most of the participants), having only 3 trainings is something that needs to be examined and provided interventions for development. Being a BNS requires a sufficient amount of knowledge and competencies needed to perform the duty of being a nutrition ally of the health authorities of the nation.

Number of Awards Received. Of the 155 respondents, 15 had received awards for their exemplary performance (9.7%), one got 2 awards and fourteen received 1 award apiece. It is not surprising to note that most of the BNS participants have no awards and recognition received from any award-giving body at the time the data gathering process was conducted. Hence, more relevant and systematized trainings are needed in order to address this issue.

Competencies of the Barangay Nutrition Scholars

Table 2. *Competencies of the Barangay Nutrition Scholars*

Compe tence Level	Planning		Coordinating				Implementation				Monitoring And Evaluation				Resource Mobilization				Documentation And Record Keeping					
	BNS		MNA		BNS		MNA		BNS		MNA		BNS		MNA		BNS		MNA					
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%				
Very Comp etent	1	11	1	7.	3	21	1	10	4	27	2	14	5	33	3	23	1	6.	8	5.	3	23	1	10
Comp etent	7	.0	1	1	4	.9	6	.3	2	.1	3	.8	2	.5	6	.2	0	5		2	6	.2	6	.3
Comp etent	6	42	6	41	5	32	5	38	5	34	6	40	5	37	6	43	3	22	4	28	4	30	6	38
Moder ately Comp etent	6	.6	4	.3	1	.9	9	.1	3	.2	3	.6	8	.4	7	.2	5	.6	4	.4	7	.3	0	.7
Slightl y Comp etent	4	25	4	31	4	29	5	36	4	26	4	31	2	17	3	20	2	18	4	26	4	29	4	30
Not Comp etent	0	.8	9	.6	5	.0	7	.8	1	.5	9	.6	7	.4	2	.6	9	.7	1	.5	5	.0	7	.3
Very Comp etent	2	12	2	13	1	9.	1	9.	1	9.	1	9.	1	7.	1	7.	4	27	3	21	1	10	1	12
Comp etent	0	.9	1	.5	5	7	4	0	4	0	4	0	2	7	2	7	3	.7	4	.9	6	.3	9	.3
Not Comp etent	1	7.	1	6.	1	6.	9	5.	5	3.	6	3.	6	3.	8	5.	3	24	2	18	1	7.	1	8.
Comp etent	2	7	0	5	0	5	8		2		9		9		2	8	.5	8	.1	1	1	3	4	

The BNSs were asked to assess their competence, in a range from 1 (not competent) to 5 (very competent), across six dimensions including planning, coordinating, implementation, monitoring and evaluation, resource mobilization, and documentation and record keeping. The competence of the BNSs was also assessed by their respective MNAOs across the six dimensions, using the same scale. The resulting frequency and percentages for both self-ratings and observer-ratings are reported in Table 2.

Planning. Majority of the BNS and MNAO respondents were rated as competent, which is indicated by 42.6% and 41.3% respectively

in the planning category of their competence as nutrition scholars. Only a small percentage of the samples from both categories of respondents were rated as not competent to perform their duties in the area of planning. This is indicated by 7.7% for BNS respondents and 6.5% for MNAO respondents. Planning is an importance competence as barangay nutrition scholars. This result suggests that there is a need to give more emphasis to the small percentage of respondents who obtained the said rating of “not competent.”

Coordinating. A large percentage of the BNS and MNAO respondents were rated as competent in the coordination aspect of their competence, which is indicated by 32.9% and 38.1%, respectively. Similar to the previous categories, only a small percentage of the samples from both categories of respondents were rated as not competent to perform their duties in the area of coordinating. This is indicated by 6.5% for BNS respondents and 5.8% for MNAO respondents. The results suggest that despite some of the trainings conducted, there is still a small percentage of respondents who obtained a rating that is classified to be not competent. Coordination is a competence needed by every barangay nutrition scholar and ensuring competent scholars in the area of planning is imperative.

Implementation. It is evident that majority of the BNS and MNAO respondents were rated as competent in the implementation aspect of their competence, which is indicated by 34.2% and 40.6%, respectively. A small percentage of the samples from both categories of respondents were rated as not competent to perform their duties in the area of implementation. This is indicated by 3.2% for BNS respondents and 3.9% for MNAO respondents. It is clear that implementation is one of the highest areas of competence among the respondents. Nonetheless, it is needful to ensure that all barangay nutrition scholars are competent in this area of implementation since this is the core competence in terms of their duties.

Monitoring and Evaluation. Similar to the results in the previous categories of competence, it was revealed that majority of the BNS and MNAO respondents were rated as competent in the monitoring and evaluation aspect of their competence, which is indicated by 37.4% and 43.2%, respectively. It can be gleaned from the table that a small percentage of the samples from both categories of respondents were rated as not competent to perform their duties in the area of monitoring and evaluation. This is indicated by 3.9% for BNS respondents and 5.2% for MNAO respondents. Monitoring and evaluation needs to be improved in terms of the competencies of the barangay nutrition scholars. As shown in the results, there are still some respondents who obtained a rating that is also classified that is not competent. It clearly suggests that these barangay nutrition scholars need some intervention program in the form of training.

Resource Mobilization. Different from the previous results, it was revealed that majority of the BNS respondents obtained a slightly competent rating only, which is indicated by 27.7%. However, majority of the MNAO respondents were rated as competent in the resource mobilization aspect of their competence, which is indicated by 28.4. It can be gleaned from the table that there was a considerable number of respondents in both categories of respondents who were rated as not competent to perform their duties in the area of resource mobilization. This is indicated by 24.5% for BNS respondents and 18.1% for MNAO respondents. The said results suggest that this is one categories of their competence that obtained a high number of cases who were classified to be incompetent. Resource mobilization is one of the most complicated set of tasks that need to be mastered by the barangay nutrition scholars in order to perform their duties in an efficient manner.

Documentation and Record Keeping. The results indicate that a large percentage of the BNS and MNAO respondents were rated as competent in the documentation and record keeping aspect of their competence, which is indicated by 30.3% and 38.7%, respectively. A small percentage of the samples from both categories of respondents were rated as not competent to perform their duties in the area of coordinating. This is indicated by 7.1% for BNS respondents and 8.4% for MNAO respondents. Record keeping is an essential aspect in the duties of barangay nutrition scholars. The aforesaid results imply that this area needs to be improved as well.

In summary, as reflected in Table 03, the BNSs perceived themselves as “moderately competent” in planning and in mobilizing resource, with mean ratings of 3.34 and 2.67, respectively. They perceived themselves as “competent” in coordinating, documenting and record keeping, implementing, and monitoring and evaluating, with mean ratings ranging from 3.45 to 3.77. Meanwhile, the MNAOs rated the BNSs as “moderately competent” in mobilizing resource, planning, documenting and record keeping, and coordinating, with mean ratings ranging from 2.85 to 3.36, and “competent” in implementing and in monitoring and evaluating, with mean ratings of 3.45 and 3.59, respectively.

Table 3. *Summary of Respondents' Level of Competence*

<i>Variables on Competence</i>	<i>BNS</i>		<i>MNAO</i>	
	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Planning	3.34	Moderately Competent	3.27	Moderately Competent
Coordinating	3.45	Competent	3.36	Moderately Competent
Implementation	3.61	Competent	3.45	Competent
Monitoring and Evaluation	3.77	Competent	3.59	Competent
Resource Mobilization	2.67	Moderately Competent	2.85	Moderately Competent
Documentation and Record Keeping	3.50	Competent	3.34	Moderately Competent
Overall	3.46	Competent	3.36	Moderately Competent

Furthermore, it can be observed that observer-ratings are lower than the self-ratings, with the exception of resource mobilization. A sizable gap between the mean self-rating and mean observer-rating exists for both coordinating and documenting and record keeping, resulting to disagreement of perceptions between the BNSs and MNAOs as to the level of competence in the two dimensions or areas.

As evidenced by a rather substantial gap between the mean ratings of 3.46 and 3.36, the overall assessment result of the two groups likewise contradicts, with the BNSs viewing themselves as “competent” and the MNAOs assessing the BNSs as only “moderately competent”.

It is evident that the BNS were competent in both the implementation and the monitoring and evaluation aspects of their performance. This is indicated in both the self-rating and the MNAO’s rating. The high level of competence in this aspect of their performance could be attributed to their previous trainings and in-service workshops or seminars that they have attended. Implementation is always emphasized in their regular tasks as BNS while it is mandatory for their performance to be monitored and evaluated which makes them more exposed to such processes.

Nonetheless, the weakest aspect of their performance as BNS is in terms of planning and resource mobilization. This could be attributed to the inherent process in the BNS program wherein planning is not shared by the stakeholders. In other words, planning is mostly made from top level management to the lower level of the organizational structure. Another reason is the fact that these BNS participants have not been fully trained in planning and resource mobilization processes. Resource mobilization entails a lot of bureaucracy in the field and appropriate training and workshop need to be conducted in order for them to be highly competent in these processes.

In the studies of Etherton et al (2015), Chan et al (2014), Klement (2010), Hughes (2013), Taburnal (2017), and Quitevis (2011), the different aspects related to the performance of BNS were emphasized. For example, the importance of additional strategies to improve nutrition education of health care professionals was highlighted. In order to improve their competencies in these areas, the aforesaid studies encourage the development of personalized strategies according to each volunteer's needs. Moreover, training for nutrition care professionals is essential in order to provide patients with culture-specific strategies that allow them to succeed with their health program.

To improve the weakest aspects and sustain the strengths of the BNS competencies, it is vital to consider the suggestions provided in previous studies. For example, Dagangon et al (2016), Endrina-Ignacio (2015), Faunillan et al (2018), Jao et al (2017), Sumaylo (2013), it was recommended that BNS should be encouraged to attend trainings on basic health care services and that the result would serve as a basis for future programs of the Department of Health (DOH) on their welfare. Continuous attendance to seminars and trainings and the use of the intervention bundle is highly encouraged to enhance their performance.

Comparison between BNS and MNAO Ratings on Competence

The mean ratings from the BNSs and MNAOs, across variables on or dimensions of competence, were compared using t test to determine whether differences are significant at 0.05 level of significance. A computed t-value with a corresponding p-value less than or equal to the indicated level of significance suggests sufficient statistical evidence for the existence of a significant mean difference. The t test results are shown in Table 05.

The null hypothesis was rejected in terms of the similarities of the respondents’ competence in the areas of implementing, monitoring and evaluating, and documenting and record keeping. As reported in Table 05, there exist significant differences in mean ratings for competence in implementing, monitoring and evaluating, and documenting and record keeping, with p-values of 0.016, 0.009 and 0.029, respectively, which are far below the level of significance of 0.05. Mean ratings from MNAOs across the indicated three variables or dimensions are significantly lower than the mean self-ratings of the BNSs. These results indicate that the MNAOs perceive the BNSs to have a substantially lower competence level in implementing, monitoring and evaluating, and documenting and record keeping compared to what is reflected in the self-assessment of the BNSs.

Table 4. *t-Test for BNS and MNAO Mean Ratings on Competence*

<i>Variables on Competence</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. Planning	0.850	0.396	Not Significant
2. Coordinating	1.217	0.225	Not Significant
3. Implementation	2.424	0.016	Significant
4. Monitoring and Evaluation	2.640	0.009	Significant
5. Resource Mobilization	-1.810	0.072	Not Significant
6. Documentation and Record Keeping	2.206	0.029	Significant
Overall	1.717	0.088	Not Significant

However, null hypothesis was accepted in terms of the similarities of the respondents’ competence in the areas planning, coordinating, and mobilizing. Resource The said table suggests that there are no significant differences in mean ratings for competence in planning, coordinating, and mobilizing resource since corresponding p-values exceed the level of significance of 0.05, signifying an agreement between the ratings from the MNAOs and the self-ratings of the BNSs. There is also no significant difference between the overall ratings, as evidenced by the p-value of 0.088 which barely exceeds 0.05.

The significant difference between the self-rating and the MNAO’s rating in terms of the BNS’ implementation, monitoring and evaluation, and documentation and record keeping could be attributed to different factors. Foremost, the two groups of respondents could have different conceptualizations on the nature of these processes related to the performance of being a BNS. Put simply, the BNS might have rated themselves very highly in these areas.

The significant difference in the ratings in these categories could be explained partly by the Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) Theory, which was developed by Rogers (1962). It highlights the different levels of acceptance of changes or innovations in every organization or institutional system. The process of adaption or diffusion of the said changes or innovation is affected by several factors and must be addressed by the organization for a specific health-related behavior to be adapted by all stakeholders in the organization. Using the proposition of this theory, it can be said that the MNAOs have a different concept or standard of the BNS performance rating because over time, the standards for BNS competencies is believed to be of vital importance to them and, as part of a social system, they adopt a new idea, behavior, or product conceptualization of BNS competence or skills.

Consequently, it is noteworthy to remember that there was a significant difference between the self-rating and the MNAO's rating in terms of the BNS' overall performance, planning, coordinating, and resource mobilization. This implies that the BNS participants the MNAOs share the same standards in terms of rating the aforesaid performance competencies. Despite the discrepancy in the ratings of the three competence factors, the overall rating of both raters (that is, the BNS participants the MNAOs) are significantly the same.

Values Practiced by Barangay Nutrition Scholars

The BNSs were also asked to conduct a self-assessment of their level of practice of certain values, in a scale ranging from 1 (not practiced) to 5 (highly practiced), which include integrity, transparency, efficiency, equity, excellence in work, respect for human rights, and accountability. Using the same scale range, their respective MNAOs were also asked to rate them on these values. Table 6 shows the Respondents practice of values in frequency and percentage while Table 7 reflects the summary mean ratings across the indicated variables on values.

Table 5. Respondents' Level of Practice of Core Values

Core Values	Highly Practiced		Practiced		Moderately Practiced		Fairly Practiced		Not Practiced											
	BNS		MNAO		BNS		MNAO		BNS		MNAO									
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%								
Integrity	66	42.6	56	36.1	50	32.3	76	49.0	36	23.2	19	12.3	3	1.9	4	2.6	0	0.0	0	0.0
Transparency	36	23.2	15	9.7	70	45.2	82	52.9	32	20.6	43	27.7	13	8.4	12	7.7	4	2.6	3	1.9
Efficiency	18	11.6	5	3.2	45	29.0	62	40.0	51	32.9	52	33.5	25	16.1	24	15.5	16	10.3	12	7.7
Equity	25	16.1	11	7.1	51	32.9	71	45.8	40	25.8	44	28.4	30	19.4	18	11.6	9	5.8	11	7.1
Excellence	34	21.9	11	7.1	51	32.9	67	43.2	42	27.1	48	31.0	16	10.3	18	11.6	12	7.7	11	7.1
Respect	51	32.9	33	21.3	60	38.7	81	52.3	28	18.1	29	18.7	11	7.1	10	6.5	5	3.2	2	1.3
Accountability	44	28.4	25	16.1	60	38.7	67	43.2	34	21.9	38	24.5	13	8.4	20	12.9	4	2.6	5	3.2

Integrity. Majority of the BNS respondents highly practice integrity as a core value, which is indicated by 42.6%. Majority of the MNAO respondents practice integrity as a core value, which is indicated by 49.0%. A small percentage of the samples from both categories of respondents fairly practice integrity as a core value. This is indicated by 1.9% for BNS respondents and 2.6% for MNAO respondents. The results suggest that the BNS had a higher level of practice of their integrity based on their self-assessment than that of the MNAO. It is also important to note that there is a need to cultivate this value to those who obtained a low level of practice ratings.

Transparency. A large percentage of the BNS and MNAO respondents practice transparency as a core value, which is indicated by 45.2% and 52.9%, respectively. It is surprising to note that a small percentage of the samples from both categories of respondents do not practice transparency as a core value. This is indicated by 2.6% for BNS respondents and 1.9% for MNAO respondents. Being transparent in their reporting and dealings with the local residents and their superiors is important in the performance of their duties. Hence, the results suggest that these BNS who obtained a "no practice" rating need to undergo further training and workshops.

Efficiency. It was affirmed that majority of the BNS moderately practice efficiency as a core value, which is indicated by 32.9%, while majority of the MNAO obtained the rating of 40%. A small percentage of the samples from both categories of respondents do not practice efficiency as a core value. This is indicated by 10% for BNS respondents and 7.7% for MNAO respondents.

Equity. Majority of the BNS and MNAO respondents practice equity as a core value, which is indicated by 32.9% and 45.8%, respectively. It is surprising to note that a small percentage of the samples from both categories of respondents do not practice equity as a core value. This is indicated by 5.8% for BNS respondents and 7.1% for MNAO respondents. Equity as a core value is important for each BNS in order to perform their duties effectively. The results imply that there is a need to at least eliminate the "no practice" ratings obtained by some of the BNS in the local community. This can be addressed with the use of the training development plan that is presented in the last section of this chapter.

Excellence in Work. It is evident from the results that majority of the BNS and MNAO respondents practice excellence in work as a core value, which is indicated by 32.9% and 43.2%, respectively. A small percentage of the samples from both categories of respondents do not practice excellence in work as a core value. This is indicated by 7.7% for BNS respondents and 7.1% for MNAO respondents. In order to perform the duties effectively and efficiently, it is important to practice excellence in all aspects of one's work specifications. The findings imply that the BNS need to enhance this area of their practice. They might just be performing their duties at the minimum level but not at the level of excellence or a level that exceeds the expectations.

Respect for Human Rights. The results reflect that majority of the BNS and MNAO respondents practice respect for human rights as

a core value, which is indicated by 38.7% and 52.3%, respectively. A small percentage of the samples from both categories of respondents do not practice respect for human rights as a core value. This is indicated by 3.2% for BNS respondents and 1.3% for MNAO respondents. As BNS, it is important to practice respect for the human rights of the target clientele in all their dealings and interactions. As implied by the results, some BNS in the local community need to develop this core value of the respect for human rights.

Accountability. A large percentage of the BNS and MNAO respondents practice accountability in work as a core value, which is indicated by 38.7% and 43.2%, respectively. A small percentage of the samples from both categories of respondents do not practice accountability in work as a core value. This is indicated by 2.6% for BNS respondents and 3.2% for MNAO respondents. Accountability is inherent in the core competencies of BNS because they have important roles to play in the nutrition of the local residents. Having a small percentage of BNS who do not practice such values is alarming to note. Hence, a development and training plan is proposed at the end of this study in order to address the said areas of concern.

In summary, as can be gleaned from Table 7, self-assessments of the BNS indicate that they “practiced” values of integrity, transparency, excellence in work, respect for human rights, and accountability, with mean ratings ranging from a high of 4.04 to a low of 3.53. However, they only “moderately practiced” values of efficiency and equity, with mean ratings of 3.24 and 3.40, respectively. Assessments of the MNAOs reveal a very similar result, indicating that the BNSs “practiced” values of integrity, transparency, respect for human rights, and accountability, with mean ratings ranging from a high of 4.02 to a low of 3.59. MNAO assessments further indicate that BNSs only “moderately practiced” values of efficiency, equity, and excellence in work, having mean ratings of 3.20, 3.38 and 3.40, respectively.

Table 6. Summary of Respondents' Level of Practice of Core Values

Variables on Values	BNS		MNAO	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
1. Integrity	4.04	Practiced	4.02	Practiced
2. Transparency	3.75	Practiced	3.67	Practiced
3. Efficiency	3.24	Moderately Practiced	3.20	Moderately Practiced
4. Equity	3.40	Moderately Practiced	3.38	Moderately Practiced
5. Excellence in Work	3.53	Practiced	3.40	Moderately Practiced
6. Respect for Human Rights	3.88	Practiced	3.83	Practiced
7. Accountability	3.82	Practiced	3.59	Practiced
Overall	3.66	Practiced	3.58	Practiced

Moreover, it can be noted that BNSs and MNAOs differ only in their assessment on the level of practice of excellence in work. While BNSs indicate that they “practiced” excellence in work, MNAOs deemed this value as only “moderately practiced” by the BNSs. Although mean ratings from MNAOs across the indicated seven values are all lower than those from BNSs, overall mean ratings from both groups (3.66 and 3.58) signify the same level of practice of the values taken collectively.

It is apparent that the weakest areas in the values of the BNS based on self-rating and MNAOs' rating are in the areas of efficiency and equity. This implies that more value formation endeavors need to be set in place for the BNS participants of the local community. The results indicate that integrity, transparency, respect for human rights, and accountability are the strongest areas in the values and attitudes of the BNS. This finds support in the study of Kenga (2018) wherein their research results indicate that community health volunteers' mean attitudes score was interpreted to be positive.

The aforesaid results on the positive attitude of the BNS (as reflected in their integrity, transparency, respect for human rights, and accountability) are supported also in the studies of Gopalan et al (2012), Alaba et al (2017), and Oendo (2017), wherein they reported similar attitudinal inclinations of their respondents. For example, Gopalan et al (2012), affirmed that the level of motivation in the work performance of the health workers is affected by the personal and social factors. Hence, it was proposed by Oendo (2017) that trainings geared towards healthcare workers must consider the perceived role expectations and the LGUs should offers training recommendations to barangay health center administrators and BHW program planners.

Comparison between BNS and MNAO Ratings on Values

BNS and MNAO mean ratings, across variables on values, were also compared using t test to determine whether mean differences are significant at 0.05 level of significance. A computed t-value with a corresponding p-value less than or equal to the indicated level of significance suggests sufficient statistical evidence for the existence of a significant mean difference. The t test results are shown in Table 7.

Table 7 shows that the null hypothesis was rejected on the basis that there is significant difference between BNS and MNAO mean ratings on the extent of practice of accountability, with a p-value of 0.001 that is way below the 0.05 level of significance.

Specifically, MNAO mean rating is significantly lower than BNS mean rating which signifies that MNAOs assessed BNS to have practiced accountability at a lesser extent than what BNSs perceived.

Table 7. *t* Test for BNS and MNAO Mean Ratings on Values

Variables on Values	<i>t</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation
1. Integrity	0.506	0.614	Not Significant
2. Transparency	1.254	0.212	Not Significant
3. Efficiency	0.457	0.648	Not Significant
4. Equity	0.302	0.763	Not Significant
5. Excellence in Work	1.712	0.089	Not Significant
6. Respect for Human Rights	0.780	0.437	Not Significant
7. Accountability	3.250	0.001	Significant
Overall	1.551	0.123	Not Significant

On the other hand, it can be said that the null hypothesis is accepted on the basis that there is no significant difference between BNS and MNAO mean ratings for the remaining six variables on values since corresponding *p*-values are way above 0.05 level of significance. BNS overall mean rating is also not significantly different from MNAO overall mean rating.

The aforesaid findings simply imply that both the BNS and the MNAOs have the same role expectations and observations on the values exhibited by the BNS participants themselves. This result is contradictory to the findings of Kenga (2018), wherein self-reported practices among the volunteers varied and that most of the participants in the study respectively advised to have appropriate feeding and healthcare services. Unlike the study of Kenga (2018), the present research revealed significantly ratings of the different groups of respondents.

Relationship between BNS Profile and BNS Competence and Values

Various measures of association were computed and tested for significance to determine whether statistically significant relationships exist between the profile variables and the level of competence and practice of certain values among BNSs as assessed by BNSs themselves and their respective MNAOs. Results are displayed in Tables 8 and 9, respectively.

Table 8. Coefficients of Correlation/Association between BNS Profile and BNS Competence and Values as Self-rated

Profile Variables	Competence		Values	
	Coefficient	<i>p</i> -value	Coefficient	<i>p</i> -value
Agea	0.175*	0.030	0.167*	0.038
Sexb	0.048	0.557	0.090	0.267
Civil Statusc	0.090	0.746	0.037	0.977
Educational Attainment	0.215*	0.007	0.145	0.071
Length of Service	0.262*	0.001	0.229*	0.004
Number of Trainingsa	0.265*	0.001	0.261*	0.001
Number of Awards	0.077	0.341	0.114	0.157
Prevalence of Malnutrition	-0.140	0.083	-0.102	0.205

Note. aPearson's *r*, bPoint-Biserial (*r_{pb}*), cEta (η), dSpearman Rho (*r_s*). *Significant at $\alpha = 0.05$

The null hypothesis is rejected in favour of the research hypothesis. Hence, there are significant positive relationships between age of the BNSs and their level of competence ($r = 0.175$, $p = 0.030$) and practice of core values in the workplace ($r = 0.167$, $p = 0.038$). This suggests that older BNSs tend to demonstrate high levels of competence and practice of core values, with the relationship between age and competence being stronger than that of age and practice of core values.

There exists a significant positive relationship between educational attainment and level of competence of the BNSs ($r_s = 0.215$, $p = 0.007$). This signifies that BNSs who attained or completed higher education levels have higher levels of competence compared to those who completed only lower education levels.

Length of service is also significantly and positively correlated with level of competence ($r = 0.262$, $p = 0.001$) and practice of core values in the workplace ($r = 0.229$, $p = 0.004$), with the association of length of service with competence being much stronger than its association with practice of core values. That is, BNSs serving for many years already or beyond the novice level tend to display high levels of competence and observe more the practice of core values.

Number of trainings or seminars attended is likewise significantly and positively correlated with level of competence ($r = 0.265$, $p = 0.001$) and practice of core values ($r = 0.261$, $p = 0.001$). This indicates that more trained BNSs tend to execute their duties and responsibilities with high level of competence and observe more the practice of core values.

On the other hand, the variables sex, civil status, number of awards received, and prevalence of malnutrition are not significantly associated with level of competence and practice of core values; likewise, educational attainment is not significantly associated with level of practice of core values, as evidenced by corresponding *p*-values exceeding the level of significance of 0.05.

It is apparent that certain demographic factors affect the competence of practice and core values among BNS. This includes age, length of service, and number of trainings. This is supported in the research of Chung (2017) which affirmed that age variables and education

or training factors were the significant predictors of the level of performance. In their study, it was shown that respondents below 45 years old performed better than those who were beyond 45 years old. This is similar to the present research wherein majority of the BNS participants in the age group from the said age group had high level of competence. Chung (2017) also had similar findings on the correlation between education and competence, wherein the majority of the respondents with higher educational had better work performance than those with primary education only.

The aforesaid results find similar directions with that of Aseo et al (2018) which affirmed the different environmental factors had significant influence or effect on the the performance of the research participants or community health workers. These factors include the sociocultural practices, access and availability of the health services, and the policies and frameworks of public health program implementation. In the same manner, Kenga et al (2018) also affirmed that sociodemographic factors had significant correlation with the competencies and attitudes of the health care workers. These were also significantly related to their demographic background such as their age, education level, and working hours. This implies that in recruiting, selecting, and retention of BNS, these factors should be given emphasis.

When level of competence and practice of core values as rated by the MNAOs were paired with the profile variables, only four statistically substantial associations were found, including those between: age and competence level ($r = 0.169$, $p = 0.035$), length of service and competence level ($r = 0.303$, $p < 0.001$), length of service and practice of core values ($r = 0.253$, $p = 0.001$), and number of trainings attended and practice of core values ($r = 0.201$, $p = 0.012$). The positive correlation coefficients indicate that the increase in level in one of these four profile variables is associated with the increase in level of competence and practice of core values in the work environment.

Table 9. Coefficients of Correlation/Association between BNS Profile and BNS Competence and Values as Rated by MNAO

Profile Variables	Competence		Values	
	Coefficient	p-value	Coefficient	p-value
Agea	0.169*	0.035	0.122	0.130
Sexb	-0.058	0.476	-0.018	0.824
Civil Statusc	0.189	0.137	0.124	0.504
Educational Attainmentd	0.073	0.368	0.028	0.734
Length of Servicea	0.303*	<0.001	0.253*	0.001
Number of Trainingsa	0.151	0.061	0.201*	0.012
Number of Awardsa	0.064	0.432	0.057	0.481
Prevalence Rate of Malnutritiond	-0.185*	0.021	-0.129	0.110

Note. aPearson's r , bPoint-Biserial (r_{pb}), cEta (η), dSpearman Rho (r_s). *Significant at $\alpha = 0.05$

In addition, there is a significant negative relationship between prevalence rate of malnutrition and level of competence ($r_s = -0.185$, $p = 0.021$). In other words, low number of malnutrition cases is associated with high level of competence, or equivalently, high number of malnutrition cases is associated with low level of competence among BNSs.

It is evident that in similar manner, the length of service and the number of trainings attended have significant correlation with the competence and core values of the BNS based on the ratings of MNAO. In the same line argument, this significant correlation between the demographic profile and focal variables could be attributed to the level of knowledge and skills obtained during the years of service and the competencies that the BNS have obtained in their training. That is to say that, regardless of sex, civil status, number of awards received, and prevalence of malnutrition, the level of competence and values of practice may not be affected.

This leads to the important generalization that regular and relevant trainings need to be implemented in the local community in order to continually improve the quality of service among BNS. Hughes (2013) argued that it is important to be aware that performance and core skills are dynamic in nature, which means that it can change as a response to the environment or other factors. Tabernal (2017) also suggested that professional trainings such as seminars related to the competencies of health care workers are vital in improving the performance of the same. Quetivis (2011) supported this proposition by stating that BHWs should be mandated to participate trainings on core health services in order to address the need to improve the skills of BNS and provide support for their welfare. Alaba et al (2017) proposed similar premises by explaining that age and training affect the performance of health workers in the local community. The knowledge of BHWs and their attitudes have a significant relationship with their practices; hence, BHWs should participate in seminars and training programs conducted by the City Health Office.

Predictors of Competence and Practice of Core Values

Standard Multiple Regression Analyses were performed to determine the significant predictors of level of competence and practice of core values among BNSs from a set of profile variables. The relative or individual contributions of the significant predictors were assessed by looking into the corresponding standardized coefficients or beta-weights. Analyses results are presented in Tables 11 and 12 for both BNS and MNAO ratings.

Results of regression analysis show that educational attainment is a significant predictor of competence ($B = 0.401$, $p = 0.010$), but not of practice of core values in the workplace ($B = 0.227$, $p = 0.112$). It can be noted that when all other predictor variables are held

constant, the competence level of BNSs who are at least high school graduates is higher by a magnitude of 0.401 than those whose educational attainment is at most high school level.

Table 10. *Unstandardized and Standardized Coefficients of the Predictors of the Competence and Practice of Values as Self-Assessed by BNSs*

Predictor Variables	Competence			Practice of Core Values		
	B	β	p	B	β	p
(Constant)	2.550		0.000	2.945		0.000
Age	0.005	0.063	0.561	0.005	0.070	0.528
Sex	0.213	0.030	0.706	0.544	0.085	0.297
Civil Status						
Single (Reference)						
Married	-0.152	-0.088	0.425	-0.059	-0.038	0.734
Widow	0.207	0.061	0.514	0.020	0.006	0.945
Separated	-0.064	-0.025	0.821	-0.067	-0.029	0.796
Education	0.401*	0.210	0.010	0.227	0.132	0.112
Length of Service	0.095	0.171	0.100	0.058	0.116	0.274
Number of Trainings	0.067*	0.187	0.022	0.064*	0.198	0.018
Number of Awards	0.055	0.022	0.787	0.154	0.069	0.411

Note. B = unstandardized coefficient; β = standardized/beta coefficient; p = probability value. Coding of sex: 0 = female and 1 = male. Coding of civil status: single (baseline), married (1 = yes and 0 = no), widow (1 = yes and 0 = no), separated (1 = yes and 0 = no). Coding of education: 0 = at most high school level and 1 = at least high school graduate.

Meanwhile, the number of trainings or seminars attended by the BNSs significantly predicts both competence ($B = 0.067$, $p = 0.022$) and practice of core values ($B = 0.064$, $p = 0.018$). Unstandardized coefficients indicate that attending an additional training or seminar, given all other predictor variables are fixed, yields positive changes in the level of competence and practice of core values among BNSs by comparable magnitudes of 0.067 and 0.064, respectively, which are rather small effects.

Furthermore, standardized coefficients indicate that educational attainment ($\beta = 0.210$) has a stronger effect than training ($\beta = 0.187$) on level of competence. And training has stronger effect on level of practice of core values ($\beta = 0.198$) than on level of competence ($\beta = 0.187$). On the other hand, as indicated by p-values exceeding 0.05 level of significance, the variables age, sex, civil status, length of service, and number of awards received are not significant predictors of competence and practice of core values.

Table 11. *Unstandardized and Standardized Coefficients of the Predictors of the Competence and Practice of Values as Assessed by MNAOs*

Predictor Variables	Competence			Practice of Core Values		
	B	β	p	B	β	P
(Constant)	2.664		0.000	3.153		0.000
Age	-0.005	-0.065	0.558	-0.005	-0.079	0.484
Sex	-0.177	-0.026	0.746	0.029	0.005	0.950
Civil Status						
Single (Reference)						
Married	0.238	0.146	0.197	0.126	0.092	0.424
Widow	0.333	0.103	0.277	0.300	0.110	0.252
Separated	0.385	0.159	0.157	0.181	0.089	0.436
Education	0.211	0.117	0.159	0.121	0.080	0.343
Length of Service	0.150*	0.287	0.008	0.107*	0.241	0.026
Number of Trainings	0.018	0.052	0.531	0.037	0.131	0.121
Number of Awards	0.022	0.009	0.912	-4.096E-5	0.000	1.000

When MNAO ratings were used as basis for determining levels of competence and practice of core values among BNSs, only length of service was found to be a significant predictor of either criterion variable. That is, length of service affects competence ($B = 0.150$, $p = 0.008$) and practice of core values ($B = 0.107$, $p = 0.026$). When all other variables are fixed, level of competence and practice of core values increase by magnitudes of 0.150 and 0.107, respectively, for an increase of one year in length of service among BNSs. Meanwhile, the relative effect of length of service on competence ($\beta = 0.287$) is stronger than its relative effect on practice of core values ($\beta = 0.241$).

It can be implied from the findings of the research that based on the BNS self-ratings, only the number of trainings or seminars attended by the BNSs significantly predicts both competence and practice of core values. It was also affirmed that educational attainment has a stronger effect than training on level of competence but on values. The significance of the frequency of trainings and educational attainment as predictors for both competence and practice of core values is attested also in the research of Sunguya et al (2013), Chung et al (2017), Kuule et al (2017), Aseyo et al (2018), Chatio et al (2019), Ngugi et al (2018). To be specific, Sunguya et al (2013) also affirmed the effect of training on health workers' knowledge and competencies in terms of nutrition-related topics.

On the same line of argument, it can be put forward that both number of trainings and educational attainment variable belong to the

same domain, which can be classified as training or education. Hence, the results imply that in order to achieve an excellent level of performance, competence, and values among BNS, relevant training programs and should be proposed. As significant predictors of both competence and values among BNS, health agencies along with the LGUs of the local community may develop training modules that are suitable to the needs of the current BNS of the different barangays. In fact, it was suggested by Sungaya et al (2013) that continuous professional development training significantly improves the performance and level of competence of health care workers in the community particularly in managing nutrition-related problems. Kuule (2017) also explained that more seminars and trainings are linked to improved performance in the delivery of required services related to health and nutrition.

Moreover, based on the ratings of the MNAOs, an important finding of the study is that only length of service was found to be a significant predictor of either criterion variable, which means that the length of service affects competence and practice of core values. Length of service on competence is stronger than its relative effect on practice of core values. Similar to the recommendations of Quetivis (2011) and Taburnal (2017), trainings and length of service affect one's competence and must be considered in the retention of BNS.

Length of service has some conceptual similarities to the number of trainings and educational attainment because as one gains years of experience, it is expected that one also gains opportunities to attend relevant trainings and continue one's educational attainment. This is supported in the study of Alaba et al (2017) wherein it was affirmed that among all the socio-demographic factors, only age, which is related to the length of service, is significantly related to the level of knowledge of the barangay health workers. Thus, in planning training programs, priority should be given to the novice or newly recruited BNS because it is assumed that their level of competence needs to be developed and enriched.

On a theoretical note, the research findings affirm the verity of the Social Ecological Model (SEM), which highlights the impact of individual and social or environmental variables that affect behaviors such those behaviors related to health promotion, health choices and decisions, and preferences and perceptions towards the appropriate health behaviors within organizations (Stokols, 1996). As mentioned in the preceding chapter of this research, the said theory emphasizes that personal, interpersonal, community or society, organization-related, and policy factors affect the behavior or performance of an individual such as one's competence and values. In relation to the results of the study, it can be pointed out that educational attainment, years of experience of service, and the numbers of relevant trainings attended are part of one's individual and interpersonal aspects. As such, the educational attainment, years of experience of service, and the number of relevant trainings is said to be best predictors of competence and core values of the BNS.

As indicated in the research findings, many of the sociodemographic factors have significant correlation with the competence and core values of BNS. Affirms the theoretical underpinnings of Contingency Theory, which postulates that any organizational behaviour is influenced by social factors among others and it highlights the need to consider social, legal, political, technical and economic factors in any organizational process or operations. Because educational attainment, years of experience of service, and the number of relevant trainings is part of sociodemographic profile that are found to have significant correlation with the focal variables of the study, it is logical to state that certain assumptions of the Contingency Theory were verified to be highly relevant in this study.

Another theoretical affirmation that can be gleaned from the aforementioned research findings are the assumptions of Systems Approach Theory, views social organizations, such as barangay health groups, are embodied by their complexity, levels of connectedness between organizational elements, degree of openness, elements of balance, and plurality of objectives (Huse and Bowditch, 1973). Using this assumption, it is vital to highlight the significant differences in the ratings between the self-rating of the BNS and the ratings of the MNAOs. As presented earlier in this chapter, the two groups of respondents had some significant differences in some areas of their rating of competence and core values. This can be explained by the System Theory which emphasized the complexity of a particular system such as that of the barangay community wherein the BNS have separate sets of standards from the MNAOs.

The significant correlation between the attitudes and competence of the nutrition workers in various barangays of the study could also be explained in terms of the Systems Theory. This is because the theory highlights the interrelatedness of the different variables in the organizations, including sociodemographic factors. Hence, the affirmation of this theory in the light of the research findings imply that the health implementing authorities and the LGUs need to collaborate in order to address the complex systems that are at play in the local community.

The Development Program for Barangay Nutrition Scholars in Eastern Visayas (DPBNSEV)

Rationale

The Development Program for Barangay Nutrition Scholars in Eastern Visayas (DPBNSEV) is a proposed plan of action that was formulated based on the empirical results of the dissertation conducted in Region 8. The development program tackles areas of concern reflected in the results of the study. This includes the different sociodemographic variable considerations, weak core competencies as BNS, and the weak areas in the practice of core values related to the performance of duties as BNS.

Addressing the findings based on the sociodemographic factors inherent among the current BNS of Eastern Visayas is needful in implementing a relevant and effective program delivery spearheaded by the Department of Health in collaboration with the different

government agencies and stakeholders. By focusing on the weak core competencies that need to be improved among the BNS, the implementation of the program would be more efficient and effective. Including the weak areas in the practice of core values related to the performance of duties as BNS in the formulation of this development plan adds sustainability to the entire program implementation since core values are more intrinsic in nature that drive all other competencies.

Objectives

The following are the objectives of the Development Program for Barangay Nutrition Scholars in Eastern Visayas (DPBNSSEV):

To implement a developmental training program for BNS in Eastern Visayas in accordance to their sociodemographic orientation;

To enhance the capacity of the BNS by addressing their weak core competencies; and

To incorporate sustainability in the implementation of the current BNS program in Eastern Visayas by improving their weak core values

Strategies Inherent in the Development Program for BNS

In order to implement nutrition programs with success, a scheme that focuses on the role of the Barangay Nutrition Scholars should be given emphasis. This includes strategies that are based on the objectives of implementing a developmental training program for BNS in Eastern Visayas in accordance to their sociodemographic orientation, enhancing the capacity of the BNS by addressing their weak core competencies, and incorporating sustainability in the implementation of the current BNS program in Eastern Visayas by improving their weak core values.

BNS Recruitment Campaign Caravan. This program will be used in order to encourage distributed socio demographic categories to participate in the program. This is an aspect of the major objective of the development plan, which is to implement a developmental training program for BNS in Eastern Visayas in accordance to their sociodemographic orientation. It is expected that after its implementation, there will be an equal distribution of BNS across sociodemographic sectors after 3 years. This means that many interested and qualified residents of Eastern Visayas will be informed with this information campaign caravan. Distribution among age groups, educational levels, gender, and civil status will be equalized and normally distributed, giving more access to various interested sectors to be a BNS.

Table 12. *The Development Program for Barangay Nutrition Scholars in Eastern Visayas (DPBNSSEV)*

<i>Areas of Concern</i>	<i>Objectives</i>	<i>Strategies</i>	<i>Specific Programs</i>	<i>Success Indicators</i>
Socio-demographic Considerations	To implement a developmental training program for BNS in Eastern Visayas in accordance to their socio demographic orientation	Encourage distributed socio demographic categories to participate in the program	BNS Recruitment Campaign Caravan	There is an equal distribution of BNS across socio demographic sectors after 3 years
		Design relevant training based on the educational attainment of the BNS	Cluster-Based BNS Training Series	80% of the BNS have received trainings based on their socio demographic cluster
		Develop local training programs for the BNS	Annual Regional BNS Training Program	90% of the BNS have attended at least 1 annual regional training program
Weak Core Competencies	To enhance the capacity of the BNS by addressing their weak core competencies	Ensure the entry of competent BNS participants	Development of BNS Recruitment Manual	A complete manual has been published as basis for BNS recruitment
		Enhance the resource mobilization competencies of the BNS	3-Day Workshop on Resource Mobilization for BNS	85% of the BNS have above satisfactory rating in resource mobilization based on the annual performance audit
		Improve the planning competencies of the BNS	Live-In Workshop on BNS Planning Competencies	90% of the BNS have above satisfactory rating in planning based on the annual performance audit
Weak Core	To incorporate sustainability in the	Ameliorate the general competencies of the BNS	Municipal Level Seminar on BNS Competencies	80% of the BNS have above satisfactory rating in the overall competencies based on the annual performance audit
		Improve efficiency as a core value among BNS	Forum on How to Improve Efficiency as	85% of the BNS have at least very satisfactory rating in terms

Values	implementation of the current BNS program in Eastern Visayas by improving their weak core values	Enhance equity as a core value among BNS Foster general improvement of the core values of the BNS	BNS Equity Implementation Workshop among BNS Search for the Most Outstanding BNS (Based on Core Value Criteria)	of efficiency as a core value 85% of the BNS have at least very satisfactory rating in terms of equity as a core value 80% of the BNS have at least very satisfactory rating in terms their overall practice of core values inherent in their duties
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Cluster-Based BNS Training Series. This program will be used in order to design relevant training based on the educational attainment of the BNS. After its implementation, it is expected that 80% of the BNS will have received trainings based on their socio demographic cluster. For example, BNS who finished secondary level of education will have a different training from those who finished an undergraduate degree. In similar manner, BNS who belong to the younger age groups will have a different clustered training form those who belong to the older age groups.

Annual Regional BNS Training Program. This program will be used to implement the strategy of developing a relevant local training program for the BNS. It is expected that at the end of the said program, 90% of the BNS have attended at least 1 annual regional training program. This is to address the findings in the sociodemographic variables, particularly on the lack of relevant trainings among BNS in the local community.

Development of BNS Recruitment Manual. To ensure the entry of competent BNS participants, the development of BNS Recruitment Manual is imperative. A complete manual must have been published as basis for BNS recruitment at the end of the first year of BNS implementation under this scheme. This program also addresses the general objective of implementing a developmental training program for BNS in Eastern Visayas in accordance with their socio demographic orientation

3-Day Workshop on Resource Mobilization for BNS. In order to enhance the resource mobilization competencies of the BNS, it is needful to implement a 3-Day Workshop on Resource Mobilization for BNS. It is expected that at the end of the workshop, 85% of the BNS have above satisfactory rating in resource mobilization based on the annual performance audit

Live-In Workshop on BNS Planning Competencies. To improve the planning competencies of the BNS, the Live-In Workshop on BNS Planning Competencies need to be promulgated. At least 90% of the BNS will have above satisfactory rating in planning based on the annual performance audit once the said workshop is implemented.

Municipal Level Seminar on BNS Competencies. As noted in the earlier empirical findings, there is a need to ameliorate the general competencies of the BNS. Hence, the Municipal Level Seminar on BNS Competencies is needful in order to have at least 80% of the BNS to have above satisfactory rating in the overall competencies based on the annual performance audit.

Forum on How to Improve Efficiency as BNS. One of the weakest core values of the BNS in Eastern Visayas is efficiency. Through this program, at least 85% of the BNS have at least very satisfactory rating in terms of efficiency as a core value. The forum will tackle the core values of efficiency and will be facilitated by the different stakeholders such as the Department of Health, Local Government Units, and other concerned private organizations.

Equity Implementation Workshop among BNS. Another weakest core value of the BNS in Eastern Visayas is equity. It is expected that at least 85% of the BNS have at least very satisfactory rating in terms of equity as a core value due to this program strategy. Similar to the previous workshop on efficiency capacity building, this workshop focusing on equity will be facilitated by the aforesaid stakeholders.

Search for the Most Outstanding BNS. The Search for the Most Outstanding BNS is imperative in order to foster general improvement of the core values of the BNS. At least 80% of the BNS have at least very satisfactory rating in terms their overall practice of core values inherent in their duties once this is implemented. The current award system will be enhanced to include the value criteria in the selection of the Most Outstanding BNS. Sustainability in the delivery of effective and efficient barangay nutrition services is achieved through the cultivation of intrinsic qualities of the BNS. Intrinsic motivation is more sustainable than the development of core competencies. Hence, the development of core competencies discussed in the previous section is a prerequisite to this aspect.

The sociodemographic data revealed an unequal representation of BNS in terms of the different sociodemographic categories such as age, gender, educational attainment, civil status, and number of trainings attended. In terms of the level of competence, most BNSs perceived themselves as “moderately competent” in planning and in mobilizing resource, while BNSs perceived themselves as “competent” in coordinating, documenting and record keeping, implementing, and monitoring and evaluating. It was affirmed that there were significant differences in mean ratings for competence in implementing, monitoring and evaluating, and documenting and record keeping, while there are no significant differences in mean ratings for competence in planning, coordinating, and mobilizing resource. In terms of the core values practiced, it was affirmed that the BNS “practiced” the values of integrity, transparency, excellence in work, respect for human rights, and accountability while they only “moderately practiced” values of efficiency and equity on the other hand, MNAOs indicates that the BNSs “practiced” values of integrity, transparency, respect for human rights, and accountability BNSs only “moderately practiced” values of efficiency, equity, and excellence in work. Further, there is significant difference between

the BNS and MNAO mean ratings. It is important to note that there was a significant positive relationship between age, educational attainment, length of service, and the number trainings attended of the BNSs with their level of competence and practice of core values in the workplace. Educational attainment is a significant predictor of competence. The number of trainings or seminars attended by the BNSs significantly predicts both competence and practice of core values. Standardized coefficients indicate that educational attainment has a stronger effect than training on level of competence. Training has stronger effect on level of practice of core values than on level of competence. As a recommendation, it was put forward that the selection criteria for BNS be reviewed and consider factors that could improve nutrition program management including gender mainstreaming criteria. It is imperative to formulate a simplified version and an extensive practical approach to nutrition education training needs to be looked into when designing and modifying the existing programs.

Conclusions

Based on the study's findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

The sociodemographic data revealed an unequal representation of BNS in terms of the different sociodemographic categories such as age, gender, educational attainment, civil status, and number of trainings attended.

In terms of the level of competence, most BNSs perceived themselves as “moderately competent” in planning and in mobilizing resource, while BNSs perceived themselves as “competent” in coordinating, documenting and record keeping, implementing, and monitoring and evaluating.

It was affirmed that there were significant differences in mean ratings for competence in implementing, monitoring and evaluating, and documenting and record keeping, while there are no significant differences in mean ratings for competence in planning, coordinating, and mobilizing resource.

In terms of the core values practiced, it was affirmed that the BNS “practiced” the values of integrity, transparency, excellence in work, respect for human rights, and accountability while they only “moderately practiced” values of efficiency and equity on the other hand, MNAOs indicates that the BNSs “practiced” values of integrity, transparency, respect for human rights, and accountability BNSs only “moderately practiced” values of efficiency, equity, and excellence in work.

Further, there is significant difference between the BNS and MNAO mean ratings.

It is important to note there was a significant positive relationship between age, educational attainment, length of service, and the number trainings attended of the BNSs with their level of competence and practice of core values in the workplace.

Meanwhile, results of regression analysis show that educational attainment is a significant predictor of competence. The number of trainings or seminars attended by the BNSs significantly predicts both competence and practice of core values. Standardized coefficients indicate that educational attainment has a stronger effect than training on level of competence. Training has stronger effect on level of practice of core values than on level of competence.

It could be advanced that the selection criteria for BNS be reviewed and consider factors that could improve nutrition management program including gender mainstreaming criteria.

It is imperative to formulate a simplified version and an extensive practical approach to nutrition education training needs to be looked into when designing and modifying the existing programs.

There is a need to study the gaps of BNS program implementation and recommend security of tenure for BNSs.

As important recommendation is to review and amend PD 1569, include the conduct an exhaustive consultation with all the BNS in the country to come-up with a better version of the policy that will reflect the needs and aspirations of the BNS.

Recognition and reward scheme must be enhanced in order to motivate BNS to excel more in their function.

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